

Analysis of Development Prospect and Security Crisis in Nigeria

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Abstract

Elucidating development and security crisis in Sub-Sahara Africa with a bird eye view on Nigeria has been an issue worthy of consideration. This result from conflicts, insurgencies, and internal wars that characterise Nigeria as well as Post-Colonial African States. The study investigate development prospect and security crisis in Nigeria. The research paper affirms that the prevailing security challenges confronting the Nigerian state are structurally entrenched and deeply rooted in development crises. This vacuum has led to societal maladies such as economic disparities, ethno-religious divides, inequality, unemployment, poverty, and marginalisation, to mention a few thus, transcending into a national security problem, which now seems to threaten the unity of the State. Adopting the methodology of qualitative approach with the use of secondary data and content analysis, the research adopts the Political Instability Theory in analysing development prospect and security crises in Nigeria. The study finds that institutional corruption, economic disparities, ethno-religious divide are some of the factors enhancing development and security crises in Nigeria. The study concludes that the problems of development and security crises will persist in Nigeria so far security problems are treated differently from developmental challenges. The research paper recommends the tackling the problem of unemployment in Nigeria, collaboration with the international community as a means of litigating development problems and security crises in the Nigerian state.

Keywords: Development, Security, Sub-Sahara Africa, Nigeria, Corruption

Introduction

The search for stability, as well as development, is undoubtedly the holy-grail for Sub-Sahara African states; it is an endless, laborious, yet elusive quest for the circumstances that would allow these nations

to create the institutions and frameworks necessary to guarantee political stability, economic growth, equitable wealth distribution, and public accountability. Despite how difficult this may seem, it is nevertheless possible to make the case that all nations, both developing and non-developing alike, strive to reach a specific level. Each nation strives to have a strong and diverse economy, a cohesive internal society, and political stability for its people. It depends on a variety of circumstances, largely internal ones, how and to what extent these goals are realised. Resources, both natural and human, are important, to start. But the power to harness resources for the general good mostly falls under the purview of administrative competence, technological know-how, and political leadership. Consequently, a capable, strong leadership is required. These, particularly in Africa, are not plentiful in many nations. The issue of national security, as defined by these nations' capacity to protect their territorial integrity and, more crucially, as a means of ensuring internal peace and stability, is one that is closely tied.

However, in order to do this successfully, threats that can lead to insecurity for the state, such as unemployment, poverty, and disparity, both existing and potential, must be reduced. It goes without saying that this cannot be achieved without development that correctly and aggressively addresses these issues. So, caught in this unbreakable tango, security as defined by national development is the primary challenge facing third-world nations. For them, discussing internal security without corresponding thought to the issue of national development is pointless, like chasing a shadow.

This research paper's aim is to offer a basic framework for studying Sub-Sahara States' rising level of insecurity with a special reference to the Nigerian state in the past decade. The Nigerian state is selected as the research case study as a result of some significant factors. Firstly, Nigeria has the largest population in the continent of Africa (Ucha, 2010). As a result, other African states have a critical strategic stake in its security. Consequently, unlike, the Federal Republic of Cameroon, the collapse of the country's governmental structures will significantly impact sub-regional security for the entire continent. Secondly, many people continue to be perplexed by the Nigerian states' failure to grasp and use its vast materials and human resources successfully. Rich in both natural as well as human resources, Nigeria serves as a prime illustration of how a once-promising third-world state could go from the mantra of developing to under-developing and sadly to de-developing as a result of years of inefficacy and inefficiency, mismanagement, political corruption, and weak democratic institutions (Ogunleye-Adetona, 2010). The level of state's growth and development ultimately influences the level of protection and security of a state at any given time, as this research work demonstrates in its construction of the framework by integrating the conceptions of security and development. This is demonstrated by the research work's premise that there is a relationship between the conceptions of national security and national development, and that a state's national security situation is determined by its level of inequality, poverty and unemployment. The research study begins with an overview of the conceptions of development and security, establishing the relationship between the two, and then moves on to an ontological investigation of the significant factors (variables) to Nigeria's underdevelopment and security challenges.

The variables is considerably more pressing and evident in many African nations as well. A growing population explosion and a corresponding decline in political accountability and economic productivity and; caused by many years of high levels of political corruption, poor leadership, weak institutions, and a lack of the ability to transform their human and material resources, turned these nations into veritable incubators for the emergence of violent anti-state groups whose ideology would lead them to commit acts of violence against the state (Stern and Ojendal, 2010). This philosophy has been largely fueled by the state's disregard of, or inability to change, its citizens' ambitions for a meaningful, purposeful, and high-quality life over the years. Due to this, many of them began to lose their legitimacy. On the one hand, tribal and/or religious loyalty clashes with state loyalty, while on the other, albeit crime, extreme anarchy, violence, and lawlessness threaten the state's continuous integrity, territorial integrity and stability.

Statement of Problem

Over the years, Sub-Sahara African states and indeed Nigeria have been plagued with numerous challenges that have hindered its development prospects and security efforts ranging from terrorism, insurgency, kidnapping, armed robbery to ethno-religious conflicts which has left it vulnerable to security threats. Despite concerted efforts by the government to address these issues through various policies and initiatives such as the establishment of security agencies and community policing programs, these problems still persist. Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive approach that involves tackling fundamental economic issues while implementing measures that promote peacebuilding and conflict prevention at all levels.

Objectives of the study

The research paper seeks to address the following objectives:

- i. To elucidate the indices enhancing development and security crisis in Sub-Sahara African states with keen reference to the Nigerian state.
- ii. To recommend substantial means of addressing national security problems, which eventually lead to developmental issues.

Literature Review

Conceptual Clarification of Development

Development is a subjective and frequently disputed idea (Kolade, 2012). However, there are some specific development benchmarks that can be reached and are generally accepted. For example, it is simple to make the case that every human community aspires to powerful, effective, and dynamic political and economic institutions that anticipate their citizens' needs and provide them rapid, appropriate attention. It is likewise feasible to claim that any society has minimal standards that all of its members must uphold which include having access to functioning healthcare services, access to clean

water, access to high-quality educational training for all people, and having an equal chance in the political sphere where competing based on meritocracy is preserved over other factors. These are all ideals that cut through cultural barriers. Therefore, if our perception of development is situational in any way, it may primarily depend on the viewpoints from which it is viewed. This explains why people frequently attempt to separate the components of national development into separate topics. As a result, one often hears of economic, social, political, religious, and cultural development as if it were possible to analyse development properly without incorporating these factors and using a holistic approach. According to Gopinath (2008, p. 91), who contends that the only way to evaluate development is monetarily; a developing state is one where "there is a large potential to enhance the per capita living standard" of its citizens. This is undoubtedly a legacy of the intellectual division that dominated developmental studies in the early 60s and late 1970s, when most of development frameworks got their theoretical base from mainstream economics. In that idea, economic expansion was seen as a necessary component of development and was broadly accepted as the primary goal of the decolonised states of Asia and Africa (Korbi, 2015).

Even in these isolated theories, a prevailing view suggests that a fundamental revolution occurs across time and distance due to a steady drip effect. As a result, development is nothing more than a characterisation of a particular state where an object's physical development and maturity advance in synchrony. When referring to human societies, development simply denotes a situation; or states that involves improvements in the quality and quantity of life for every community member. We refer to a situation as under-development when there is a comparable drop or retrogression in the standard of living for a sizable percentage of an entire population (Rodney, 1972). Development as well as underdevelopment, in essence, denote a relational condition in which one precisely reflects the lack of the other.

Development is conceptualised as qualitative improvement, quantitative growth, and enlargement in the capabilities, powers, and choices of individuals, communities, or institutions (Mirakhor and Askari, 2010). According to Mogilevsky (2010), development is defined as "the change of the biosphere as well as the application of man's financial, non-living and living resources to meet human wants and similarly enhance lives; quality of life." A common theme across all views of development is the understanding that raising everyone's standard of living is both development's fundamental aim and its primary objective. The focus is very much on skill-building and empowering among society's people so they can improve their living circumstances. The most analytical and concise conceptualisation of development is still provided by Dudley Seers, who addresses essential political and socio-economic issues and attempts to connect them to human development. Seers (1972) claims; *"the inquiries to make in regards to a nation's development are... What is the current State of poverty? What is the current state of unemployment? What has inequality been up to lately? It is clear that there has been a period of development for the nation in question if all three of these have decreased*

from greater levels. Even if per capita income doubled, it would be unusual to refer to the outcome as "development" if one or more of these issues have been getting worse, especially if all three have."

Thus, rather than emphasising economic growth based on abstract data, the emphasis is placed on the individual as a crucial component of society and the subject of any transformation. This study contends that this theory of development offers a superb analytical foundation from which a proper justification for the connection between security and development can be drawn. The three signs that Seers present serve as an instructive foundation for this paper's analysis.

The Concept of Security

Political scientists and other security scholars have never responded satisfactorily to the question of what security in contemporary times actually entails. This is because, its perception changes over time. For example, most publications in the mainstream study of security until recently explicitly conceptualise State's capacity to protect its national sovereignty from threats, either real or imagined and other prospective adversaries. States construct and outfit their armed forces to accomplish this. This conception's central tenet is that threats and hostility of force are successfully deterred by a state's ability to use violence against an adversary (Akinbi, 2015). On a national level, there is a misconception that all that is needed to safeguard a state is its national law enforcement and other domestic intelligence tools.

But in the post-Cold War age, there is a clear shift in what security means. There is currently an effort to widen it to include more pertinent, if not essential, components within this conceptualisation. Today, issues like economic growth and development, political equality, good governance and accountability are necessary to any thorough analysis and assessment of the security concern. Perhaps this is due to the customary militaristic view of security that predominated Cold War discourse, which proved ineffective and utterly unable to satisfy security aspirations among many states. This new idea places a priority on human development. As a result, we observe in this change a new and expanded notion of security, which refers to a state's ability to protect itself against external dangers using all available means and challenges by ensuring the general socio-economic welfare of its citizens and populace (Enobi, 2016). Here, there exists a clearer understanding of the significance of additional issues, such as environmental, political, social and economic concerns, as essential elements of any nation's security (Buzan and Hansen, 2009).

According to Enobi (2016), security is a reasonable degree of certainty at many levels within the social system, from local communities to the international level. Here, it is understood that there is an existence of order at the international level that depends on the predictability of the actions of other system participants. Thus, security at the local level comprises the state's capacity to foresee the foreseeable effects of any given circumstance on its residents. The ability of the state to maintain law and order, though that may be significant, does not hold the key to success; rather, it is in the creation of the required socio-economic conditions that ensure a reasonable degree of predictability on the behaviour of its residents. For our purposes, security is a condition of diminished or contained tension

and dangers in which the stability of a given state is not immediately threatened from both the inside and the outside. Here, stability is defined as the pattern, order, and regularity that, over a long period of time, typified the State's position.

Security and Development Challenges in the Nigerian state: The Three Indices

From the national or domestic security standpoint, several conclusions may be drawn from Nigerian state threat analysis over the past ten years. One, unlike, for example, South and North Korea, Pakistan and India, or Kuwait and Iraq prior to the start of the Gulf War, Nigeria does not face an imminent threat from its neighbours. The Nigerian state rises way above all of its neighbours in terms of its economic as well as its military prowess, making it nearly impossible for any of the sub-Saharan states to declare open enmity. Despite maintaining a love-hate relationship with Cameroon on the eastern side for several years over a disputed region, the (ICJ) International Court of Justice in The Hague eventually settled the conflict. Second, the Nigerian state has never engaged in open conflict with any superpower powerful enough to attack it, except the Murtala and Abacha administrations. However, even those conflicts between the United States under Murtala and Abacha were, in the researcher's perspective, State's efforts to cement its sovereignty and rule over the African continent. Therefore, the research might characterise them as a struggle for hegemony and domination in African political affairs between an existing global superpower and an aspiring continental superpower. Third, it would be impossible and immoral for Nigerian state to attack another nation in the continent due to its status as 'big brother' and the prestige it commands in the continent of Africa. International law approved every one of its military incursions, which were numerous in other countries. All of these support the strong claim that Nigeria's key security risks will almost entirely come from inside and be based on socio-economic and political inequalities. These fundamental problems have been ingrained over many years in Nigeria's sociopolitical and economic systems. A single-line economy and problems like extreme poverty, tribalism, major corruption, bad government, and almost no industrial foundation are frequently referred to be traits of developing nations. While this may be the case, it is crucial to note that in the case of the Nigerian state, these traits have persisted for a very long time, making it difficult for any deliberate effort to promote national growth. By the turn of the 20th century, all vestige of political responsibility and people-centered leadership had been gone due to decades of military control combined with an inefficient and corrupt bureaucracy.

After 1999, Nigerians had a resurgence of optimism and hope that the socio-economic and political development difficulties impeding the State's development and progress would be resolved. The election of a new democratic government administration, first of its kind in about twenty years, was a significant factor in this confidence (Okeyim, 2013). Six general elections as well as twenty-three years after the initial change later, Nigeria's situation could be characterised as a precipitous decline into worsening (Aniekwe & Kushie, 2011). The country is currently on the verge of collapse as it faces the

harsh realities of a failing state. These hopes, optimism, and longings that came with democracy have now been replaced with disillusionment and dissatisfaction. The violent conflicts, armed group interactions with the State on an intra-tribal, tribal, and religious level, the prevalence of urban crime, and the sense of insecurity all serve as outlets for this rage and frustration.

In addition, it would not be overstating things to argue that gradually over the past ten years, the State has lost its exclusive right to use force. Nigeria has earned the reputation of a failing, if not failed, State in this millennium, thanks to organisations like the Bandits, Boko-Haram, Herdsmen in the Northern part of the country, IPOB in the East, Odua People's Congress (OPC) in the Western part of the country, kidnapping and armed robbery roaming the highways in the Southern part of the country. Reviewing the story of the nation's economic development and growth over the past 50 years is essential to understanding how the nation has been reduced to this depressing display. This will give us a foundation for understanding how various internal security threats have evolved over time.

According to Nwagboso (2021), the most pitiful aspect of the Nigerian state is that the bulk of its citizens live in a condition of deprivation while the other fairly minority; are thriving in wealth and prosperity. The fact that the Nigerian state has not had any appreciable economic growth and progress in its six-two years as a sovereign state is economically significant. A good example of this is the pace of economic growth from 1966 and 1997, which varied between 0.1% and \$790 per capita on average, well below the \$1,060 overall mean for West African States (Nwagboso, 2021). Nigeria is richly blessed with a vast amount of material and human resources, but it has repeatedly shown that it is unable, or most likely not ready, to use these plentiful resources for its growth. One of the top eight crude oil producers, its economy is a conventional single centered because royalties and rent from oil exports provide virtually all of its industrial base. Oil and agricultural profits made up 2.7% and 89%, respectively, of all foreign revenues in the years immediately after the country gained independence. Currently, there's a reversal of role where the agricultural industry, which was once the foundation of rural economies, has all but disappeared, and exports of crude oil make up more than 90% of all foreign revenues as of the turn of the last century (Nwagboso, 2021). This has a very evident consequence. Since most rural residents who are under, or unemployed move to metropolitan areas in pursuit of white-collar jobs, creating a rich pool of incompetent workforce, it causes a huge increase in urban impoverishment (Nwagboso, 2021). The Nigerian state's socio-economic conditions are summarised by Meredith, (2006) as;

Amid a \$280 billion oil fortune, the economy was in disarray, public services were consistently ineffective, hospitals and schools were falling apart, higher education had all but collapsed, the roads were littered with potholes, and the communication network hardly worked. Power outages were common, as well as domestic gasoline supply difficulties. Nigeria citizens were, in general impoverished in 2020 more than they were in the early 1970s, at the beginning of the oil boom. At \$310, the income per head was less than one-third of what it was in 1980. The vast majority of people had no access to clean water and survived on less than 50 cents per day. Approximately half of younger children

were stunted due to inadequate nutrition, and nearly one-fifth of toddlers died before turning five. Without access to basic facilities, lots of its citizens resides in slums surrounded by decaying piles of trash.

Nigeria was placed by the World Bank at the bottom of twenty-five of nations in terms of human development indices in 2009, with states like Ghana, Zambia, and Kenya ranking higher. These indicators measure literacy levels, accessibility to health facilities and clean water, human nutrition, mortality rates, and rates of malnutrition (Khalid, 2009). Over 100 million Nigerians, according to a similar National Bureau of Statistics survey from 2010, are in extreme poverty leaving on less than \$1 per day (BBC, 2012). These statistics are noteworthy because they were acquired during the surges of economic and institutional reforms that the Obasanjo's government initiated in late 1999 and early 2000. One could speculate on the numbers if the reforms were not implemented at all. For instance, employment indices in the Nigerian state rose from 163 in 2000 to 1,867 in 2004 (Akinbi, 2015). The impact this unfavourable trend has on the citizens is best understood in the context of the current degree of insecurity in the nation, arguably due to inefficient economic resource management.

The study has highlighted that both economic and political factors might be used to explain this underdevelopment in Nigeria, while it also observed how inadequate economic progress produces a category of poor and dissatisfied majorities in the State. The only thing left for us to do is to look at this dilemma's political aspect. For a thorough analysis of law, order, and development in a third-world country, political action—defined in terms of political accountability and strong, effective public institutions—is essential. This is so because there is an unbreakable connection between political progress a human development. Democratic culture and values must control all decision-making and fundamental governance processes where political growth and accountability and openness are significantly mature.

This is very important in heterogeneous societies like the Nigerian state because it creates the conditions for the peaceful resolution of various religious and sociocultural problems. As a result, the level of security in the nation strongly correlates with the character of the political institutions and leadership, as well as their understanding of social challenges, dynamism, and response to the desires of the people. If the political establishment is found to be dishonest and unaccountable, the democratic ideals and ambitions of the populace will be suppressed. In this situation, the ruling class's personal political objectives took and priced the public interest. In the end, this invariably creates an atmosphere of mistrust, suspicion, dread, and alienation, where the rage that has been suppressed finds a violent outlet.

Since the country's independence, political developments in the Nigerian state have generally followed the typical African tendency, in which the civilian political establishment and military elites alternately control the majority of African governments. This makes it simple to draw a few conclusions about the structure of the acquisition of power and its abuse in different states. In general, elite 'power' politics determine public events at every given moment, and as a result, the mindset of the ruling elites determines how national politics act at any given time. But in contrast to a call to nation-building based

on the values of equality, tolerance, constitutionalism and the rule of law, the prevalent practice defines politics as a zero-sum game in which the winner takes all (Tar and Shettima, 2010). In actuality, constitutionalism never goes further than the mindset that it is a rule that can be broken without repercussions for the typical African and particularly the Nigerian state political class. Because of this, implementing democratic practices is famously challenging.

In the Nigerian state, the return to a democratic dispensation in 1999 succeeded in creating an impunity culture among the power elite in all levels of governmental structure, where corruption, absolute stealing of the state purse, gross abuse of constitutional norms, provisions and principles, and violent, competitive pressure for political supremacy maintains control. This level of success was unprecedented in the country's political history (Iyekepolo, 2020). The most significant effect of this scenario, which the political elites create, is that they not only encourage corruption, mediocrity, and nepotism but also undermine democracy, commit electoral fraud, encourage religious divisions and ethnic sentiments in the Nigeria state for their selfish political gains, and generally create a sense of confusion and hopelessness about the precise direction the nation is going. By focusing on corruption, the political elite inadvertently creates the conditions that ultimately lead to the State's present security problems.

Theoretical Framework

Political Instability Theory

The theory of Political Instability is adopted for this research paper. The Political Instability Theory is a school of thought in international relations that seeks to explain the causes and consequences of development and security crises in countries (Lipsy, 2020). According to this theory, development challenges and security crisis arise when there is a mismatch between the expectations of the people and the ability of the government to meet those expectations (Lipsy, 2020). From this perspective, static development and security crises can be seen as a result of either a lack of legitimacy or capacity on the part of the government. If the government is perceived as illegitimate by its citizens, it may engage in protests, riots, or even violent uprisings to remove it from power. On the other hand, citizens may become frustrated and disillusioned with their leaders if the government lacks the capacity to provide basic services such as security, infrastructure, education and healthcare.

The consequences of political instability are often dire for both domestic and foreign actors. In many cases, it leads to economic decline, social unrest and an increase in violence which ultimately destabilises both national and regional security (Lipsy, 2020). Additionally, political instability can lead to refugee flows across borders, creating further tensions for neighbouring countries. Therefore, Political Instability Theory provides us with an important framework for understanding how challenges to development, security crisis and how governance can lead to crises that have far-reaching implications for regional stability and global security.

Methodology

The methodology adopted for this study is the qualitative research design. The qualitative research design focuses on understanding and interpreting perspectives and experiences through the collection and analysis of non-numerical data, such as interviews, observations, and documents. Similarly, the research relies mainly on secondary data of data collection. This include; published (and un-published) materials, such as: books, journals, and newspapers. Documentations on the subject matter from Libraries, lecture notes, internet etc. furthermore, data collected is analysed via content analysis. Content analysis is a research method used to study written, oral, or visual communication. It involves systematically categorizing and interpreting the content of messages using predefined criteria. The goal of content analysis is to identify patterns and themes within the data that can be used to draw conclusions about the meaning and use of language in a particular context.

Discussion of Findings

Ethnic and Religious Conflict as an Indices Enhancing Development and Security Crises in Nigeria

Ethnic and religious conflicts have proven to have a significant impact on the development and security crisis in Nigeria (Bamidele, 2020). Ethnic conflicts in Nigeria often result in the displacement of people, destruction of infrastructure, and disruption of economic activities. When different ethnic groups clash over land ownership or political power, it leads to violence that hampers development efforts. Displaced populations become vulnerable to poverty and malnutrition, as they are forced to abandon their homes and livelihoods. This hinders the overall socio-economic progress of affected regions. Also, religious conflicts further exacerbate the development challenges by dividing communities along religious lines (Gentile, 2019). Nigeria is a diverse country with a significant Muslim population in the north and a substantial Christian population in the south. Competition for resources or political dominance can be manipulated along religious lines, leading to violence between Muslims and Christians. Such conflicts not only hinder social cohesion but also damage critical infrastructure like schools, hospitals, and markets (Gentile, 2019).

In addition to impeding development, ethnic and religious conflicts pose severe threats to national security (Bamidele, 2020). They create an environment that harbours to extremism and terrorism. Radical groups exploit existing fault lines within society to recruit members who feel marginalized or disenfranchised due to ethnic or religious differences. These groups engage in acts of violence that destabilize regions and undermine government authority. Furthermore, ethnic tensions in Nigeria often lead to political instability when politicians manipulate ethnicity for personal gain (Seife, 2022). Politicians often appeal to sentiments based on tribal affiliations during elections or when vying for power. This practice fuels animosity between different ethnic groups as they perceive themselves as fighting for their own survival within the political landscape. Consequently, this undermines

democratic processes by eroding trust in the political system and sowing the seeds of division. The security crises resulting from ethnic and religious conflicts also have economic consequences. Ongoing insecurity deters Foreign Direct Investment, limits trade, and disrupts business activities (Seife, 2022). In a country like Nigeria, heavily reliant on oil revenues, this can have devastating effects on the national economy. The diversion of resources towards security operations further drains funds that could have been allocated to development projects such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure. Thus, ethnic and religious conflicts in Nigeria pose significant challenges to both development and security. These conflicts hinder socio-economic progress, promote extremism, undermine political stability, damage critical infrastructure, impede foreign investment, and drain government resources.

Economic Disparity as an Indices Enhancing Development and Security Crises in Nigeria

Economic disparities play a significant role in exacerbating development and security crises in Nigeria. The country, with its abundant natural resources and potential for growth, continues to face challenges due to the unequal distribution of wealth and opportunities. Economic disparities hinder development by perpetuating poverty. Nigeria is home to one of the largest populations living below the poverty line in Sub-Saharan Africa (Akinyetun and Ambrose, 2021). The concentration of wealth among a small percentage of the population leaves a vast majority struggling to meet their basic needs. This inequality limits access to quality education, healthcare, and infrastructure, preventing individuals from reaching their full potential (Akinyetun and Ambrose, 2021). Consequently, the lack of opportunities for upward mobility contributes to social unrest and instability.

Furthermore, economic disparities exacerbate security crises in Nigeria. High levels of unemployment among young people, especially in urban areas, create fertile ground for criminal activities such as armed robbery and drug trafficking. The absence of alternative means to sustain livelihoods compels many individuals into illegal activities as a desperate measure to survive. Additionally, instances of kidnapping for ransom have increased due to socioeconomic inequalities. These security challenges not only endanger citizens' lives but also deter foreign investment and impede overall economic growth. Moreover, economic disparities deepen ethnic and religious divisions within Nigeria. Resource-rich regions often experience marginalization as their wealth flows primarily to other parts of the country. This creates resentment and grievances that fuel conflicts between different ethnic or religious groups seeking control over resources or political power. Such tensions have led to violence and instability in various parts of Nigeria over the years.

Corruption as an Indices Enhancing Development and Security Crises in Nigeria

Corruption is a multifaceted and pervasive social phenomenon that involves the abuse of entrusted power for personal gain or advantage (Basabose, 2019). It encompasses a broad range of unethical and illegal activities, characterized by dishonesty, bribery, nepotism, embezzlement, favouritism, extortion,

and other forms of misconduct. At its core, corruption undermines the principles of fairness, transparency, accountability, and justice within societies. It distorts the functioning of public institutions and hampers socio-economic development by diverting resources away from their intended purposes. Corruption has plagued Nigeria for decades and remains one of the biggest obstacles to its development and one of the factors enhancing security crises in the polity. It permeates every sector of society, including politics, business, judiciary, and public administration (Basabose, 2019). This widespread corruption erodes trust in government institutions, undermines public services delivery, hampers economic growth, and perpetuates poverty.

Corruption and Development Challenges

Corruption intertwines with development challenges in Nigeria. The misappropriation of funds intended for developmental projects limits the country's ability to invest in critical infrastructure such as roads, electricity grids, water supply systems, and healthcare facilities. This shortfall impedes economic growth by hindering trade activities and discouraging foreign investment. Additionally, corruption undermines educational institutions by compromising academic standards through fraudulent practices like examination malpractices or “sorting” – where students bribe teachers for better grades. This erodes the quality of education provided to Nigerian youths who represent the future workforce. Inadequate access to quality education exacerbates unemployment rates among young people, creating a fertile ground for social unrest and insecurity. The development of human capital is vital for economic progress, and without proper investment in education and skills training, Nigeria's potential remains untapped.

Corruption and Security Crises

The security crises in Nigeria are multidimensional, with factors such as terrorism, ethno-religious conflicts, armed banditry, and secessionist movements contributing to instability across the nation. These issues are often rooted in socio-economic disparities, political marginalization, corruption, and weak governance. Boko Haram, an extremist group that seeks to establish an Islamic state in Nigeria, has been responsible for numerous attacks resulting in the loss of thousands of lives and displacement of millions. The group exploits grievances stemming from poverty, rampant corruption, and lack of inclusion to recruit new members. Ethno-religious conflicts fueled by competition over resources and political power have also led to violence in various regions of Nigeria. Inadequate responses from security agencies further exacerbate these tensions. Furthermore, armed banditry and kidnapping for ransom have become prevalent challenges particularly in the northern part of the country. These criminal activities not only pose a threat to individuals but also hamper economic activities as businesses struggle to operate under heightened insecurity.

Diplomacy as a Substantial Means of Addressing National Security Problems in Nigeria

Diplomacy plays a crucial role in addressing national security problems in Nigeria. As a complex and diverse nation, Nigeria faces various security challenges, ranging from terrorism and insurgency to ethno-religious conflicts and resource-based disputes. In such a context, diplomacy serves as an effective tool for resolving conflicts, fostering cooperation, and promoting stability (Muniruzzaman, 2020). Firstly, diplomacy helps in preventing conflicts by facilitating negotiations between different parties. Through diplomatic channels, countries can engage in dialogue to find common ground and resolve their differences peacefully. In the case of Nigeria, diplomatic efforts have been instrumental in managing ethno-religious conflicts that have threatened national security. Diplomatic initiatives such as interfaith dialogues and peace conferences have helped build trust between communities and bridge divides. By promoting understanding and tolerance, diplomacy contributes to reducing the tensions that often lead to violence.

Secondly, diplomacy enables countries to cooperate on matters of mutual interest, thereby enhancing regional and international security (Muniruzzaman, 2020). In Nigeria's case, diplomatic engagement with neighbouring countries is crucial for addressing transnational security challenges like terrorism and cross-border crimes. Cooperation through joint operations, intelligence sharing, and capacity building programs can significantly strengthen the collective response against these threats. Effective diplomatic relations also promote economic integration and development, which can contribute to long-term stability by addressing underlying grievances that fuel insecurity. Furthermore, diplomacy plays a vital role in mediating conflicts within the country. In Nigeria's diverse society where different ethnic groups coexist, tensions can arise over issues such as resource allocation or political power-sharing. Diplomatic processes like mediation and negotiation help bring conflicting parties together to find mutually acceptable solutions. The example of Niger Delta conflict illustrates how diplomacy has been employed successfully to mitigate tensions arising from disputes over oil resources. By engaging stakeholders through dialogue facilitated by diplomats or third-party mediators, peaceful resolutions can be achieved, thus reducing the potential for violence.

Moreover, diplomacy helps in strengthening international alliances and partnerships that enhance national security. As a member of various regional and international organizations such as the African Union and the United Nations, the Nigerian state can utilise diplomatic channels to build strategic relationships with other nations. These alliances will provide Nigeria with access to resources, expertise, and support that can bolster its security capabilities. Additionally, diplomatic efforts contribute to shaping international norms and policies that address global security challenges. By actively participating in multilateral forums, Nigeria can promote its interests while contributing to global peace and stability. Lastly, diplomacy promotes soft power strategies that complement traditional security approaches. Soft power involves influencing others through cultural exchange programs, educational initiatives, and public diplomacy campaigns (Zaharna, 2021). By engaging with other nations on cultural platforms, Nigeria can showcase its rich heritage, diversity, and potential as a

nation. This not only enhances Nigeria's image but also fosters goodwill among nations. Furthermore, diplomatic engagement can enable the state to advocate for issues of national importance such as human rights or sustainable development in multilateral forums (Zaharna, 2021). Such efforts will strengthen Nigeria's influence on the global stage and contribute to long-term peacebuilding. Thus, diplomacy serves as a valuable means of addressing national security problems in Nigeria. Through negotiations, cooperation, mediation, alliance-building, and soft power strategies like cultural exchanges, diplomacy plays a crucial role in preventing conflicts and resolving existing ones. By harnessing the power of dialogue and engagement at various levels - local, regional, continental, and global-Nigeria can effectively tackle its security challenges while promoting stability within its borders and beyond.

Conclusion

This paper concludes that the problem of insecurity will persist and continue to afflict the Nigerian state as long as the issue of national security is treated differently from the point of national development, and do not take proactive steps to address the problems of economic disparity, corruption and as well as social exclusion based on religion and tribe. This holds for other emerging states dealing with the difficulties of economic development, democratisation, and political reform, particularly those in the continent of Africa. Despite being created with the Nigerian state in mind, this framework acknowledged the similarities of the problems most Sub-Saharan African Nations confront presently. Widespread and systemic poverty, societal injustice and inequality, slow development and economic growth, shoddy democratization efforts, and corrupt and autocratic leadership continue to be some of the most prominent issues for most African nations. As a result, wars, social unrest, and young restlessness have persisted in these areas.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made from the finding;

1. Seeing national security and national development as separate issues is counterproductive and dangerous, especially for emerging states like Nigeria. As a result, decision-makers must recognise the significance of this truth and begin developing the institutions and measures that will effectively assure development, accountability, and justice in their nations. Otherwise, all efforts to combat insecurity will remain fruitless.
2. The international community cannot afford to ignore problems associated with social fairness, democracy, political reforms, and good governance in developing states. The engagement of the developed states in all domains that promote these issues in the developing states is very vital. These contribute significantly to sustainable development, progress, and peace, by extension, world peace. No one benefits when major world powers, for tactical reasons, choose to ignore flagrant abuses of human rights, poor governance, corruption, social injustice, and inequality among their

partners in developing states. Because in the end, it feeds the factors that put the world's peace in peril. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the entire international community to support emerging countries like Nigeria by insisting on good governance, a sincere democratic process, and credible leadership on the part of their leaders.

3. The challenges of unemployment should be addressed promptly as evidence has shown that unemployment breeds conflict in form of social disorder. Disorder in the polity breeds security crises while security challenges enhance the problems of development.

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